

Table S3. Comparative dental measurements (mm) of WIMF/A 4696, WIMF/A 4693, and WIMF/A4692 and previously described Lower Siwalik fossil murines.

Taxon	Elements	Specimen no.	Locality	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Max Width/Max Length (Shape)	Sq. root of Area (Size)	Age
Murinae indet.	M2	WIMF/A 4696	Ramnagar (Dehari 2)	1.30	1.00	0.77	1.14	~12.4-11.6
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	M2	7651 B	41	1.20	1.10	0.92	1.15	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	M2	19318	430	1.10	1.06	0.96	1.08	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	M2	19355	430	1.24	1.10	0.89	1.17	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	M2	19357	430	1.24	1.12	0.90	1.18	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	M2	19356	430	1.24	1.24	1.00	1.24	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	M2	19329	430	1.14	1.12	0.98	1.13	13.8
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	M2	34563	Y 311	1.30	1.02	0.78	1.15	10.2
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	M2	34238	Y 259	1.27	1.03	0.81	1.14	10.2
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	M2	36837	Y 797	1.33	1.02	0.77	1.16	11.2
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	M2	33672	504	1.15	1.05	0.91	1.10	11.6-11.2
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	M2	33649	504	1.13	0.95	0.84	1.04	11.6-11.2
"Pre- <i>Progonomys</i> "	M2	33755	76	1.08	0.92	0.85	1.00	11.6-11.2
"Pre- <i>Progonomys</i> "	M2	33664	504	1.21	1.17	0.97	1.19	11.6-11.2
<i>Karnimata darwini</i>	M2	PUA 18-75	Haritalyangar	1.68	1.59	0.95	1.63	8.85
<i>Karnimata darwini</i>	M2	VPL/RP-HM1	Haritalyangar	1.59	1.54	0.97	1.56	8.85
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	34591	Y 311	1.30	1.40	1.08	1.35	10.1

<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	34588	Y 311	1.38	1.27	0.92	1.32	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	left M2	34602	Y 311	1.35	1.30	0.96	1.32	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	left M2	34606	Y 311	1.35	1.30	0.96	1.32	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	left M2	34607	Y 311	1.30	1.25	0.96	1.27	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	54181	Y 311	1.38	1.26	0.91	1.32	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	54182	Y 311	1.60	1.30	0.81	1.44	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	54187	Y 311	1.35	1.20	0.89	1.27	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	54188	Y 311	1.50	1.30	0.87	1.40	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	54189	Y 311	1.50	1.25	0.83	1.37	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	rt M2	54192	Y 311	1.45	1.30	0.90	1.37	10.1
Murinae indet.	m1	WIMF/A 4693	Ramnagar (Dehari 2)	1.99	1.17	0.59	1.53	~12.4-11.6
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m1	19294	430	1.56	0.94	0.60	1.21	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m1	19470	430	1.54	0.90	0.58	1.18	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m1	19485	430	1.58	1.04	0.66	1.28	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m1	19452	430	1.62	1.00	0.62	1.27	13.8
Near <i>Progonomys</i> / post- <i>Antemus</i>	m1	496	33705	2.00	1.20	0.60	1.55	12.4
Near <i>Progonomys</i> / post- <i>Antemus</i>	m1	496	45013	1.86	1.17	0.63	1.48	12.4
Near <i>Progonomys</i> / post- <i>Antemus</i>	m1	496	45019	1.91	1.18	0.62	1.50	12.4
Near <i>Progonomys</i> / post- <i>Antemus</i>	m1	496	45020	1.84	1.15	0.63	1.45	12.4
Near <i>Progonomys</i> / post- <i>Antemus</i>	m1	496	45024	1.73	1.09	0.63	1.37	12.4

<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33611	76	1.56	0.90	0.58	1.18	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33773	76	1.61	1.05	0.65	1.30	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33777	76	1.51	1.00	0.66	1.23	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33780	76	1.58	0.98	0.62	1.24	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33782	76	1.54	0.87	0.56	1.16	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33793	76	1.55	1.06	0.68	1.28	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	33799	76	1.56	1.04	0.67	1.27	11.4
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	54051	809	1.52	0.97	0.64	1.21	11.3
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	54052	809	1.52	0.94	0.62	1.20	11.3
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	54055	809	1.56	0.97	0.62	1.23	11.3
<i>Progonomys hussaini</i>	m1	54056	809	1.59	0.92	0.58	1.21	11.3
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	m1	36167	Y 311	1.53	1.00	0.65	1.24	10.2
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	m1	36168	Y 311	1.58	0.98	0.62	1.24	10.2
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	m1	34159	Y 259	1.50	0.94	0.63	1.19	10.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7753	182	1.32	0.80	0.61	1.03	9.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7761	182	1.37	0.86	0.63	1.09	9.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7762	182	1.31	0.79	0.60	1.02	9.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7778	182	1.38	0.87	0.63	1.10	9.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7793	182	1.39	0.94	0.68	1.14	9.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7811	182	1.33	0.77	0.58	1.01	9.2

<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	7817	182	1.40	0.84	0.60	1.08	9.2
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	33276	367	1.37	0.86	0.63	1.09	9
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	33271	367	1.36	0.84	0.62	1.07	9
<i>Progonomys debruijini</i>	m1	33261	367	1.39	0.86	0.62	1.09	9
<i>Karnimata darwini</i>	m1	VPL/RP-HM2	Haritalyangar	1.77	1.09	0.62	1.39	8.85
<i>Karnimata darwini</i>	m1	VPL/RP-HM3	Haritalyangar	1.72	1.09	0.63	1.37	8.85
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	33204	Y311	1.70	1.05	0.62	1.34	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34515	Y311	1.75	1.10	0.63	1.39	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34516	Y311	1.85	1.10	0.59	1.43	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34521	Y311	1.60	1.00	0.63	1.26	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34524	Y311	1.80	1.10	0.61	1.41	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34528	Y311	1.85	1.21	0.65	1.50	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34529	Y311	1.60	1.05	0.66	1.30	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34530	Y311	1.90	1.15	0.61	1.48	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34535	Y311	1.80	1.20	0.67	1.47	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m1	34536	Y311	1.60	1.00	0.63	1.26	10.1
Murinae indet.	m2	WIMF/A 4692	Ramnagar (Dehari 2)	1.25	1.00	0.80	1.12	~12.4-11.6
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	7652 B	430	1.25	1.05	0.84	1.15	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19385	430	1.28	1.10	0.86	1.19	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	26273	430	1.12	0.98	0.88	1.05	13.8

<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19408	430	1.20	1.04	0.87	1.12	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19398	430	1.20	1.06	0.88	1.13	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19396	430	1.16	1.04	0.90	1.10	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19414	430	1.22	1.04	0.85	1.13	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19397	430	1.26	1.06	0.84	1.16	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19422	430	1.18	1.10	0.93	1.14	13.8
<i>Antemus chinjiensis</i>	m2	19423	430	1.36	1.08	0.79	1.21	13.8
<i>Progonomys morgane</i>	m2	33558	76	1.05	0.91	0.87	0.98	11.6-11.2
"Pre- <i>Progonomys</i> "	m2	33654	504	1.30	1.11	0.85	1.20	11.6-11.2
"Pre- <i>Progonomys</i> "	m2	33561	76	1.27	1.10	0.87	1.18	11.6-11.2
<i>Karnimata darwini</i>	m2	VPL/RP-HM2	Haritalyangar	1.36	1.18	0.87	1.27	8.85
<i>Karnimata darwini</i>	m2	VPL/RP-HM3	Haritalyangar	1.27	1.09	0.86	1.18	8.85
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34608	Y311	1.37	1.16	0.85	1.26	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34611	Y311	1.30	1.20	0.92	1.25	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34612	Y311	1.30	1.20	0.92	1.25	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34614	Y311	1.25	1.10	0.88	1.17	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34615	Y311	1.50	1.25	0.83	1.37	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34617	Y311	1.35	1.20	0.89	1.27	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34619	Y311	1.35	1.10	0.81	1.22	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34624	Y311	1.25	1.20	0.96	1.22	10.1

<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34628	Y311	1.45	1.20	0.83	1.32	10.1
<i>Karnimata fejfari</i>	m2	34631	Y311	1.40	1.25	0.89	1.32	10.1

Notes: Max Width = maximum width, Max Length = maximum length. Area = Max Width x Max Length. Comparative measurements taken from Jacobs et al. (1989), Kimura et al. (2013, 2017), Flynn et al. (2020), Patnaik (2020), and the current study.